

TEACHING READING SKILLS BY USING TECHNIQUES IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSROOM

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ABSTRACT

Reading is about understanding written text. It's also a complex activity that involves both perception and thought. Reading consists of two related processes: recognition and comprehension. Word recognition refers to the process of perceiving how written symbols correspond to one's spoken language. Comprehension is the process of making sense of words, sentences and connected text. Readers typically make use of background knowledge, vocabulary, grammatical knowledge, experience with text and other strategies to help them understand written text. A person may read in order to gain information, verify existing knowledge, read for enjoyment or enhance knowledge of the language being read. The purpose for reading also determines the appropriate approach to reading comprehension. The communicative approach to language teaching has given by instructors So the understanding of the role of reading techniques in the language classroom and the type of texts that can be used in instruction is very important.

Keywords: Reading, Comprehends, Process, Strategies, Authentic Materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reading is an essential skill for English as foreign language (EFL) students. Reading is the most important skill to master. With strengthened reading skills, EFL students will make greater progress and development in all academic areas (Anderson, 2009). The main purpose for reading is to comprehend the ideas in material. Reading involves at least three types of skills—decoding comprehension, and reading strategies (Deng Yumei, 2009). In universities, there are cases where students can read the words, sentences and passages but face a lot of difficulties in their comprehension of the main ideas. This is because of the students' lack of ability of comprehension of reading material. The issue of how to enhance teaching efficiency and develop students' reading comprehension ability is a fundamental question for English language teaching.

The aim of my reseach is to explore the teaching of reading and the role of strategy instruction. This work consists of four parts: The process of reading; Techniques for teaching reading skills and Strategies for developing reading skills; Using authentic materials and approaches.

2 THE PROCESS OF READING

Reading is a complex “cognitive process” of decoding symbols in order to construct or derive meaning. Reading is a means of language acquisition, communication and of sharing information and ideas. The purpose for reading also determines the appropriate approach to reading comprehension.

Good readers show that they can read extensively, integrate information in the text with existing knowledge, have a flexible reading style, depending on what they are reading, be motivated, rely on different skills interacting: perceptual processing, phonemic processing, recall, read for a purpose and reading serves a function.

Reading is an interactive process that goes on between the reader and the text, resulting in comprehension. The text presents letters, words, sentences and paragraphs that encode meaning. The reader uses knowledge, skills and strategies such as:

Linguistic competence: Ability to recognize the elements of the writing system; knowledge of vocabulary and how words are structured into sentences.

Discourse competence: Knowledge of discourse markers and how they connect parts of the texts to one another.

Sociolinguistics competence: Knowledge about different types of texts and their usual structure and content.

Strategic competence: The ability to use top-down strategies as well as knowledge of the language. Reading comprehension is thus much more than decoding. Reading comprehension results when the reader knows which skill and strategies are appropriate for the type of texts, and understand how to apply them to accomplish the reading purpose.

3 TECHNIQUES FOR TEACHING READING SKILLS

Teachers develop students' awareness of the reading process and reading strategies by asking students to think and talk about how they read in their native language and allow students to practice the full repertoire of reading strategies by using authentic reading tasks. When working with reading tasks in class, teachers show students the strategies that will work best for the reading purpose and the type of text and explain how and why students should use the strategies.

Teachers have students practice reading strategies in class and ask them to practice outside of class in their reading assignments and encourage students to be conscious of what they're doing while they complete reading assignments. Teachers also encourage students to evaluate their comprehension and self-report their use of strategies. They build comprehension checks into in-class and out-of-class reading assignments, and periodically review how and when to use particular strategies.

Teachers encourage the development of reading skills and the use of reading strategies by using the target language to convey instructions and course-related information in written form: office hours, homework assignments, test content. In order to raise students' awareness of reading as a skill that requires active engagement, and by explicitly teaching reading strategies, teachers help their students develop both the ability and the confidence to handle communication situations they may encounter beyond the classroom. In this way they give their students the foundation for communicative competence in the new language.

4 STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING READING SKILLS

Readers typically make use of background knowledge, vocabulary, grammatical knowledge, experience with text and other strategies to help them understand written text. Strategies that can help students read more quickly and effectively include

There are the following types of reading and the corresponding types of activities to develop the corresponding reading skills:

Previewing: Reviewing titles, section headings, and photo captions to get a sense of the structure and content of a reading selection

Predicting: Using knowledge of the subject matter to make predictions about content and vocabulary and check comprehension; using knowledge of the text type and purpose to make predictions about discourse structure; using knowledge about the author to make predictions about writing, vocabulary and content.

Skimming is reading to confirm expectations; reading for communicative tasks. Skimming is the most rudimentary type of reading. Its object is to familiarize you as quickly as possible with the material to be read.

Scanning is reading to extract specific information; reading for general understanding. Scanning is a skill that requires that you read quickly while looking for specific information. To scan a reading text, you should start at the top of the page and then move your eyes quickly toward the bottom. Generally, scanning is a technique that is helpful when you are looking for the answer to a known question.

Guessing from context: Using prior knowledge of the subject and the ideas in the text as clues to the meanings of unknown words, instead of stopping to look them up.

Close reading or searching reading is reading for complete understanding; reading for detailed comprehension (information; function and discourse). Close reading is the most important skill you need for any form of literary studies. It means paying especially close attention to what is printed on the page. Close reading means not only reading and understanding the meanings of the individual printed words, but also involves making yourself sensitive to all the nuances and connotations of language as it is used by skilled writers.

Teachers can help their students become effective readers by teaching them how to use strategies before, during, and after reading.

Pre- reading: Plan for the reading task

Set a purpose or decide in advance what to read for

Decide if more linguistic or background knowledge is needed.

Determine whether to enter the text from the top down (attend to the overall meaning) or from the bottom up (focus on the words and phrases)

While- reading: Monitor comprehension

Verify predictions and check for inaccurate guesses

Decide what is and is not important to understand

Reread to check comprehension

Ask for help.

Post- reading: Evaluate comprehension and strategy use

Evaluate comprehension in a particular task or area

Evaluate overall progress in reading and in particular types of reading tasks

Decide if the strategies used were appropriate for the purpose and for the task

Modify strategies if necessary.

5 USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS AND APPROACHES

To develop communicative competence in reading, classroom and homework activities must resemble (be) real-life reading tasks that involve meaningful communication. They must therefore be authentic in three ways.

Firstly, reading materials must be authentic: It must be the kind of material that students will need and want to be able to read when studying abroad, or using the language in other contexts outside the classroom. When selecting texts for student assignments, remember that the difficulty of a reading text is less a function of the language, and more a function of the conceptual difficulty and the task(s) that students are expected to complete.

Secondly, reading purpose must be authentic: Students must be reading for reasons that make sense and have relevance to them. “Because the teacher assigned it” is not an authentic reason for reading a text. Ask students how they plan to use the language they and what topics they are interested in reading and learning about. Give opportunities to choose assignments, and encourage them to use the library, the Internet to find other things they would like to read.

Thirdly, reading approach must be authentic: Students should read the text in a way that matches the reading purpose, the type of text, and the way people normally read. This means that reading aloud will take place only outside the classroom, such as reading for pleasure. The majority of students’ reading should be done silently. Students whose language skills are limited are not able to process at this level, and end up having to drop one or more of the elements. Usually the dropped element is comprehension, and reading aloud becomes word calling: simply pronouncing a series of words without regard for the meaning.

Studies show that when students read they improve not only their reading fluency, but they also build new vocabulary knowledge and expand their outlook also. Reading can help students write better, improve listening and speaking skills and develop positive attitudes toward reading in English.

6 CONCLUSION

This section can conclude the study, recapitulate the main findings, describe the implications of the results, and make some suggestions and recommendation. You may specifically want to:

Summarize your Study: You will provide a summary of the whole study—but not just a summary of the results.

Evaluate your Study: Judge your study in term of its significance, limitations, delimitations, generalizability, novelty, strengths, and weaknesses. Do this by:

1. Indicating limitations,
2. Indicating significance/advantage, and/or
3. Evaluating methodology.

Deduce from your research: Make suggestions concerning areas for further research or solutions to certain problems. Provide implications for teaching. Do this by:

Making suggestions,

Recommending further research, and/or

Drawing pedagogic implications.

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